

DESIGN ANALYSIS OF THE T-800 INLET PARTICLE
SEPARATOR/AIR OIL COOLER BLOWER

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents fiber layup design on Sundstrand's Inlet Particle Separator/Air Oil Cooler Blower for use on the Light Helicopter Turbine Engine Company (LHTEC-Allison/Garrett) T-800 Engine, based on dynamic and structural analysis. The blower is designed with the goals of reduced weight and comparable cost to a cast and machined aluminum blower and provides equivalent performance and meets aerospace structural requirements. This analysis is performed using ANSYS® Finite Element Package with material properties obtained using the in-house General Laminate Program for pre- and post-processing. Boundary conditions are established by the micromechanic analysis of the carbon/epoxy fabric and the mounting arrangement. The methodology of the analysis is outlined and a comparison made of the modal frequencies to that of test results.

KEY WORDS: Carbon/Epoxy; Fabric; Vibration/Structural; Finite Element; Testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

The inlet particle separator (IPS)/air oil cooler (AOC) blower is a shaft-driven, single-stage blower using a mixed-flow impeller for the LHTEC T-800 engine. The purpose of the blower is to scavenge the engine IPS and induce cooling air through the engine AOC. Sundstrand Power Systems Division is a major supplier of IPS blowers and blowers used in a wide variety of other aerospace applications.

The key drivers of the design of the LHTEC T-800 IPS/AOC blower were extremely low weight, minimal envelope, extremely low performance degradation from sand ingestion erosion, and no maintenance. These items dictated that the main inlet-housing of the blower could be manufactured from a composite structure that would be adequate to satisfy the stringent design requirements and, in particular, the MIL-STD-810C vibration specification and blade-off condition.

The main inlet-housing design requirements can be met by using carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy material and a hand layup manufacturing process. However, because of the variation in the loading

conditions, the characterization of the part's dynamic and structural response is achieved by choosing the correct stiffnesses based on ply stackup and fiber orientation. This is done by using Sundstrand's general laminate computer program to provide average orthotropic laminate elastic constants and individual ply analyses.

The ANSYS® Finite Element Code is then used to provide a detailed dynamic and structural analysis of the blower. This paper describes the methodology used in the main inlet-housing design process and a comparison of the analysis results to those from the test results.

2. T-800 IPS/AOC BLOWER DESCRIPTION

The T-800 IPS/AOC blower is a composite/aluminum shaft-driven mixed-flow blower, as shown in Figure 1. The blower consists of a fiberglass inlet duct, carbon fiber main inlet-housing with a stainless steel shroud, and a cast aluminum fan housing. The splined input shaft rotating at 24,024 rpm drives a 10-bladed impeller to draw air through the air oil cooler and provides the suction source for the inlet particle separator. The shaft is pressed into the impeller assembly, which is supported by ball bearings. A labyrinth seal provides protection against foreign object damage ingestion, and a nut secures the rotating group to the shaft. The blower can be disassembled from the engine by removing four screws on the inlet duct and removing marman clamps at both ends of the blower. A boroscope port is included for visual inspection of the blower impeller (Figure 2).

The blower assembly is designed to be cantilevered off the engine gearbox through a V-band mounting flange, ignoring the effect of the airframe-supplied overboard duct attached to the blower exit V-band flange and the support of the fiberglass inlet duct.

3. FIBER LAYUP DESIGN AND ANALYSIS APPROACH

Figure 3 shows a flowchart of the design and analysis methodology used on the composite T-800 blower main inlet-housing. The remainder of the paper outlines the major steps performed in the final iteration.

Figure 1 T-800 IPS/AOC blower

Figure 2 Cross-sectional view of the T-800 IPS/AOC blower

Figure 3 Design and analysis flowchart

4. MATERIAL SELECTION

Once the loading conditions are established, the next task is to select the composite material. Composites are layers of fibers held together by a binder or matrix. The combination of resin, fiber, lay angle, and weave patterns are nearly limitless. However, the following criteria were used in selecting the material for the main inlet-housing:

- stiffness and strength
- performance at elevated temperature
- fatigue strength
- minimum weight

- ease of fabrication
- cost and availability

HEXCEL F3T584-42-F263TM 8-harness weave carbon fabric was selected with a fiber-to-resin volume ratio of 60:40 percent and a ply thickness of 0.1905 mm (0.0075 in.). F263 is a structural, heat-resistant epoxy resin formulated for excellent translation of high modulus carbon fiber properties. Consistency is one of the chief advantages of woven fabric over other forms of reinforcement such as chopped strand mat. The woven fabric, by its nature, gives a reinforcement that is free from voids and uniform in thickness and weight. Layup has fewer problems because the fabric can be easily positioned and cut. Table 1 shows the basic material properties of the woven fabric selected.

Table 1 HEXCEL F3T584-42-F263TM material properties

	at 294°K			at 422°K		
	L	LT	ST	L	LT	ST
E _c GPa	57	57	—	57	57	—
E _t GPa	57	57	—	57	57	—
G GPa	—	5	—	—	5	—
μ	—	0.06	—	—	0.06	—
α mm/mm K *10 ⁻⁶	2.88	2.88	—	2.88	2.88	—
ρ Mg/m ³	1.60	—	—	—	—	—
F _{tu} MPa	345	345	—	345	345	—
F _{tu} MPa	310	310	—	207	207	—
F _{su} MPa	—	50	49	—	41	37

5. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element analysis was performed using ANSYS[®] finite element program interactively to generate a three-dimensional idealized structure using shell, beam, and mass elements, as shown in Figure 4. The figure does not show the internal spiders of rigid massless beams used to support the mass/spring system of the rotating assembly, allowing simulation of lateral critical speed effects in the rotating components. The mass of 1.17 kg (2.65 lb) was representative of the actual rotating mass, and the spring stiffness adjusted to give a resonant frequency of 617 Hz, corresponding to the first lateral critical speed of 37,040 rev/min. Also omitted from the figure is the lumped mass/rigid beam assembly at the open end of the rectangular duct, used to represent the remainder of the fiberglass inlet duct.

5.1 Dynamic Analysis The following distinct load cases were analyzed:

- sinusoidal vibration
- blade-off

The input spectra used in the analysis are shown in Tables 2 and 3. The tables contain only the points at the ends of straight-line segments on log-log plots of spectral values vs. frequency, because the ANSYS[®] software incorporates automatic logarithmic interpolation. Table 2, which is based on Figure 5 with a Q-factor of 12.5, is used in all three coordinate directions. The values in

Figure 4 Finite element idealized model of the T-800 IPS/AOC blower

Table 3 are equivalent to an unbalance of $1.98 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N-s}^2$ (18,150 N at 28,920 rev/min). For the blade-off case, excitation was applied only in the two coordinate directions perpendicular to the axis of the unit.

Table 2 IPS/AOC blower acceleration response spectrum used in sinusoidal vibration analysis

Frequency (Hz)	Acceleration (mm/s^2)
5	15,668
14	122,837
23	118,778
104	2,428,554
2,000	2,428,554

Table 3 IPS/AOC blower amplitude spectrum used in the blade-off analysis

Frequency (Hz)	Force (N)
5.00	24.37
500.00	243,700.00

The entire blower model, except for the mass/spring system representing the rotating components, was reduced to a single "superelement" having 162 master degrees of freedom. Plots of the first four modes shapes (the ones mainly excited by the input spectra) are shown in Figures 6 through 9, and the resulting frequencies are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 IPS/AOC blower frequencies at various excitation modes

Mode	Frequency (Hz)	Axis of Vibration
1	51.9	X & Z
2	58.0	Y
3	225.6	X & Z
4	374.6	X

Figure 5 IPS/AOC blower sinusoidal vibration input spectrum

Figure 6 Blower—first mode

Figure 7 Blower—second mode

Figure 8 Blower—third mode

Figure 9 Blower—fourth mode

5.2 Structural Analysis Structural analysis of the composite main inlet-housing was performed by using the dynamic finite element model and applying acceleration in the three directions based on the excitation modes. The frequencies and g-loads for the X, Y, and Z vibration modes are summarized in Table 5. Blade-off loads were also applied to the model in X and Y directions, with the loads shown in Table 6.

Table 5 Vibrational loads for structural analysis

	Vib-Y	Vib-X		Vib-Z	
	Mode 2	Mode 1	Mode 3	Mode 1	Mode 3
Frequency (Hz)	58.0	51.9	225.6	51.9	225.6
Acceleration	77.0 g	61.6 g	250.0 g	61.6 g	250.0 g

Table 6 Blade-off loads for structural analysis

	B/O-Y	B/O-X		
	Mode 2	Mode 1	Mode 3	Mode 4
Frequency (Hz)	58.0	51.9	225.6	374.6
Unbalance Force (N)	3,258.1	2,630.4	49,701.6	137,033.9

The maximum stresses in the element X and Y directions from ANSYS® runs were converted to mean strains and curvatures for various sections on the housing. These strains and curvatures were substituted into the Sundstrand general laminate program to analyze individual ply stresses and obtain reserve factors (RF = allowable stress/calculated stress), based on maximum stress criteria. Adequate reserve factor and fatigue life were achieved for all loading conditions.

Figures 10 and 11 show the basic ply layup and the manufactured main inlet-housing, respectively. A thermally expandable rubber/aluminum mold was used to consolidate the layup, and a detailed explanation of the process is in Reference 2.

6. VIBRATION TEST RESULTS

The blower was subjected to sinusoidal vibration in accordance with MIL-STD-810C, Method 514, Procedure I. The test was conducted with accelerometers and strain gages installed and a running speed of 2,000 rpm. Blower ambient air temperature was maintained at 156°F during vibration test.

Figure 10 Basic ply layup for main inlet housing

Figure 11 T-800 IPS/AOC blower main inlet-housing

Before the start of vibration, scans were conducted in each of the mutually perpendicular axes to obtain the blower response frequencies. The resonance test frequencies selected by LHTEC are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 T-800 blower resonance test frequencies

Y-Axis (Hz)	X-Axis (Hz)	Z-Axis (Hz)
66	66	66
180	150	450
—	—	1,800

Endurance and resonance tests were completed for each of the three axes, with the following changes detected during the tests and after high-intensity "X ray" of the main inlet-housing. Figure 12 shows areas of local delaminations.

Area (1) Local delamination area (1-in. x 1-in.) has occurred due to bending of the duct section during the 5 to 104 Hz sweep in the X-axis. We believe that this delamination caused the first mode natural frequency shift from 66 to 40.5 Hz. However, despite this delamination, the unit continued to complete the vibration and impact test for the remainder of the test without any further change in the natural frequency and completed the post-acceptance test successfully. This occurrence was in line with previous carbon fiber composite structures tested, showing a similar result. (A delamination causes a change in the natural frequency and a change in the load path, allowing the composite to keep on functioning.) A recheck of the Y-axis frequency was made after the above change, showing a shift in natural frequency from 66 Hz to 44.4 Hz.

Area (2) The delamination in this area was caused during resonance dwell at 150 Hz and 180 Hz (the natural frequency of the fiberglass adapter duct). We believe that if the adapter duct end were supported during the vibration testing (as it is on the engine), these delaminations would not have occurred. However, future production unit tabs will be strengthened for an added safety margin.

Figure 12 T-800 blower delamination areas

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Using the general laminate program to obtain average orthotropic elastic properties, along with finite element analysis technique, proved useful in analyzing composite structures linear-elastic stiffness behavior. The first mode of vibrational test results compared favorably to that of the analysis before any local delamination. Despite this delamination, the unit continued to complete the vibration and impact test for the remainder of the test without any further change in the natural frequency, and completed the post-acceptance test successfully.

A variation in predicted modal frequencies with the test results is attributed to the finite element modeling and how closely it resembles the actual manufactured component. The finite element model differed somewhat at the juncture of the cylindrical section mating the duct section, because the effect of external and internal radius was not modeled and ignored the effect of filler material.

Although the design and analysis approach provided an adequate solution to this type of structure, detail analysis was also performed at local areas such as V-band flange, bolted flange, and all critical radii. A reanalysis of the delamination areas should be performed based on ply failures and their effects on the dynamic response.

8. REFERENCES

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9. BIOGRAPHY

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